

PARAMETERS OF THE RIPPER-MOLE KNIFE

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Abstract. The purpose of the study is to substantiate the parameters of the ripper-mole knife. The technological scheme of the ripper-mole is given. To increase the stability of the drain and reduce the traction resistance, a knife is attached to the main working organ-the deep-hole, to which the drainer is attached. When the tool moves forward, a thin flat knife cuts a vertical slit in the sub-arable soil layer, which subsequently breaks due to soil deformation, and a drainer attached to the knife with a chain forms a cylindrical cavity in the soil - a mole drain. Analytical dependences are obtained for determining the height, the angle of sharpening the knife and the angle of installation of the knife to the horizon, as well as its traction resistance. Theoretical studies have established that the height of the ripper-mole knife should be 7.5 cm, the angle of sharpening 300 and the angle of installation to the horizon 220. At the same time, the traction resistance of the knife depends on the parameters of the knife, the depth of tillage and the physical and mechanical properties of the soil.

Introduction

Among the modern achievements of science and technology in the field of the theory of tillage machines that can be used to improve the technological performance of tools are the theory of cutting with a flat knife blade. Research in this area was carried out by N. Aldoshin [1], F. Mamatov [1, 5], F. Juraev [2], Y. Rajabov [3], K. Ravshanov [4, 7, 8, 12, 17, 19], K. Fayzullaev [5, 10, 12, 22], D. Chuyanov [6, 9], R. Tovashov [11, 16], U. Kodirov [12, 13, 21], S. Alikulov [14], B. Mirzaev [1, 22]. These studies have studied the basic laws of cutting the soil with flat knives. It is established that for the qualitative performance of the soil cutting process, cutting should be carried out with sliding or with longitudinal movement [2-10]. As a result, the traction force is reduced by 30 percent or more. However, the process of cutting the sub-arable soil layer with ripper-mole knives has not been studied, its parameters have not been substantiated.

The purpose of the study is to substantiate the parameters of the ripper-mole knife.

Materials and methods

To increase the stability of the drain and reduce the traction resistance, a knife 2 is attached to the main working body-the deep hole 1, to which the drainer 4 is attached (Figure 1). When the tool moves forward, a thin flat knife 2 cuts a vertical slit in the under-tillage layer of the soil, which subsequently breaks due to soil deformation, and a drainer 4 attached to the knife by a chain 3 forms a cylindrical cavity in the soil - a mole drain.

The parameters of the deep softener Blade include (Figure 2): h_b – is the height of the blade, θ is the angle of sharpening the blade, i_b – is the angle of installation of the blade relative to the base of the bend, t_b – is the thickness of the blade and the width of the blade [11-15].

We determine the height of the blade from the condition that its tip moves above the lower point of the hole. Otherwise the blade will cut off the bottom of the opening hole. This can reduce the excess energy consumption and the tightness of the walls of the hole.

According to figure 1

$$h_b = d_m + \Delta_b - \Delta_m, \quad (1)$$

in this Δ_m – is the distance from the tip of the knife to the point below the hole punch, cm.

Putting $\Delta_m=1.5$ cm, $\Delta_n=2$ cm and $d_m=7$ cm in the above expression, we determine that the height of the blade should be 7.5 cm

Figure 1. Technological scheme of the ripper-mole: 1 – deep-loader; 2 - blade; 3 – steel cable; 4 – drainer

The blade hole, which is installed in the recess before the hole punch, can be fixed in three positions in relation to the bottom of the bend, that is, to the horizon (Figure 2). As you know [2, 3], two zone deformation occurs when the upright mounted blade moves in the soil (Figure 2): softener is similar to the deformation that occurs in the process of tooth work a_1 deformation of the upper layer at depth, while in a_2 deformation, which is carried out under the influence of the lower part of the blade, the walls

Figure 2. Parameters of the pitting blade

Installing the blade at an angle $\alpha < 90^\circ$ reduces traction resistance, but a_1 enlarges the layer. Installing the blade at an angle $\alpha > 90^\circ$ increases traction resistance, but a_1 shrinks the Layer [2, 5, 8]. Therefore, it is advisable to install the blade at an angle $\alpha > 90^\circ$. There can be two cases in this: $0 < \alpha_1 < \varphi$ and $\alpha_1 > \varphi$. In the first case, the equal influencer of the elemental forces of the greater resistance is horizontal, with its steep organizer equal to zero. In the latter case, the equal influencer of the elementary forces of soil resistance deviated from normal to the direction of movement by φ . In this case, a steep organizer of the elementary forces of soil resistance occurs. This force resists the immersion of the blade and, correspondingly, the pitchfork into the soil, as a result of which the depth of its processing and, accordingly, the depth of the opening notch with the hole punch are reduced. Based on the above, it is desirable to install the blade under $0 < \alpha_1 < \varphi$ bkrchak in relation to the horizontal. Considering that the minimum value of the friction angle φ is 25° , we take $\alpha_1 = 22^\circ$.

Figure 3. Scheme for the justification of the installation of the blade in relation to the horizontal

The sharpening thread angle and thickness of the blade seam to the

previously performed studies [20, 21] we mainly accept 30° and 1.0 cm, respectively, and the width of the blade 10 cm, taking into account its tightness

Results and discussion

The pull resistance of the blade R_p consists of the sum of the pull resistance resistances of the surfaces of its blade, facet and base

$$R_b = R_{mx} + R_{fx} + R_{ax}, \quad (2)$$

B.Mirzayev [1, 4, 21] and F.Mamatov taking into account the studies of [1, 4], it is possible to determine the resistance of the soil to which the blade is exposed by the sheep expression

$$R_{mx} = \frac{H_c}{\sin \alpha_1} t_n \sigma_o \sqrt{1 + f^2} \cos(\alpha_1 + \varphi).$$

since $\alpha_1 < \varphi$ is $\varphi = \alpha_1$. Without it

$$R_{mx} = \frac{H_n}{\sin \alpha_1} t_b \sigma_o \sqrt{1 + f^2} \cos 2\alpha_1, \quad (3)$$

here F – coefficient trend; σ_r – vremennoye soprotivleniye pochvi sjatiyu, Pa;

An equal influencer of elementary normal forces acting on one side of the blade's facet can be determined by the sheep's formula [21]

$$N_{f1} = \frac{1}{2} p b_{bf} l_{bf} = \frac{q t_b^2 l_{bf}}{16 \sin \frac{i_b}{2}}, \quad (4)$$

here p – is the average specific soil pressure on the chamfer, $p=0,5qh_{bf}$; b_{bf} – is the chamfer width, m; i_f – is the knife sharpening angle, degree; h_{bf} – is the thickness of the soil layer crushed by the chamfer, $h_{bf}=t_b/2$ m; l_{bf} – is the chamfer length, m.

From Figure 3

$$b_{bf} = \frac{t_b}{2 \sin \frac{i_b}{2}}; \quad (5)$$

$$l_{bf} = \frac{H_b}{\cos \alpha_1}. \quad (6)$$

(4) we put the value of the l_{bf} by expression (7)

$$N_{f1} = \frac{q t_b^2 H_f}{16 \sin \frac{i_f}{2} \cos \alpha_1}. \quad (7)$$

since $\alpha_1 < \varphi$ is the normal that affects the facet of one side of the blade, and the equal influencer of the urinal forces is directed horizontally, its value can be determined in aries

$$R_{1fx} = \frac{q t_b^2 H_b}{16 \sin \frac{i_b}{2} \cos \alpha_1}. \quad (8)$$

Then the total resistance of the blade facades

$$R_{fx} = \frac{qt_f^2 H_f}{8 \sin \frac{i_f}{2} \cos \alpha_1}. \quad (9)$$

We determine the tensile resistance of the surfaces of the base of the blade by the expression on the insert

$$R_{ax} = 2N_a f = 2qFf, \quad (10)$$

in this f – the surface of one side of the base of the blade, m^2 .

Based on Figure 3

$$F = F_{ABC} + F_{BCDE}, \quad (11)$$

$$F_{ABC} = \frac{b_b^2}{2} \operatorname{tg} \alpha, \quad (12)$$

$$F_{BCDE} = \frac{b_b H_b}{\cos \alpha_1} - b_b^2 \operatorname{tg} \alpha_1. \quad (13)$$

We put the values of F_{ABC} and F_{BCDE} in (12) and (13) by (14)

$$F = \frac{b_b H_b}{\cos \alpha_1} - \frac{b_b^2 \operatorname{tg} \alpha_1}{2}. \quad (14)$$

To determine the tensile resistance of the surfaces of the base of the blade by placing the value of F (15), we take the following expression

$$R_{ax} = 2qf \left(\frac{b_b H_b}{\cos \alpha_1} - \frac{b_b^2 \operatorname{tg} \alpha_1}{2} \right). \quad (15)$$

By putting the values (9), (10) and (11) of R_{ym} , R_{qf} and R_{uy} in terms of expressions (16), we get the expression in the sheep to determine the resistance of the column to gravity

$$R_b = \frac{H_b}{\sin \alpha_1} t_b \sigma_o \sqrt{1 + f^2} \cos 2\alpha_1 + \frac{qt_b^2 H_b}{8 \sin \frac{i_b}{2} \cos \alpha_1} + 2qf \left(\frac{b_b H_b}{\cos \alpha_1} - \frac{b_b^2 \operatorname{tg} \alpha_1}{2} \right). \quad (16)$$

The obtained analytical expression (16) makes it possible to determine the total traction resistance of the knife depending on its parameters and the physic-mechanical properties of the soil.

4. Conclusions

To increase the stability of the drain and reduce the traction resistance, a knife must be attached to the main working body-a deep-loader, and a drainer to it. When the tool moves forward, a thin flat knife cuts a vertical slit in the under-arable soil layer, which subsequently breaks due to soil deformation, and a drainer attached to the knife with a chain forms a cylindrical cavity in the soil - a mole drain. Analytical dependences are obtained for determining the height, the angle of sharpening the knife and the angle of installation of the knife to the horizon, as well as its traction resistance. Theoretical studies have established that the height of the ripper-mole knife should be 7.5 cm, the angle of sharpening 30° and the angle of installation to the horizon 22° . The traction

resistance of the knife depends on the parameters of the knife, the depth of tillage and the physical and mechanical properties of the soil.

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